

1 **High-Pressure Experimental Data of CO₂+Mitotane and**
2 **CO₂+Ethanol+Mitotane Mixtures**
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13
14 **Abstract**

15 This work presents new experimental phase equilibrium data for mitotane in
16 supercritical CO₂ and mitone in supercritical CO₂ plus ethanol. The synthetic-
17 static method in a high-pressure variable-volume view cell was used to measure
18 the solid-fluid (SF) and the fluid-fluid (FF) equilibrium data. The phase
19 equilibrium experiments were carried out in the temperature range from (298 to
20 333) K and in the pressure range from (3.44 to 21.84) MPa. The Peng-
21 Robinson equation of state was used for describing the fluid phases, and an
22 expression for the fugacity of pure solid mitotane was used for representing the
23 solid phase. This made it possible to model the SF and FF equilibrium data for
24 the CO₂ + mitotane mixtures. Fair agreement was found between experimental
25 and calculated values.

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2 equilibrium data.

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4 **1. Introduction**

5

6 Mitotane ((RS)-1-chloro-2-[2,2-dichloro-1-(4-chlorophenyl)-ethyl]-benzene) is a
7 chiral drug used in the treatment of adrenocortical carcinoma. Nowadays, such
8 drug is marketed as a racemic mixture of their R and S enantiomers. However,
9 in most cases of chiral drugs, each isolated enantiomer presents different
10 pharmacological effects and toxicological profiles, and thus they must be tested
11 separately.

12 In two recent articles^{1,2}, Santana and his colleagues used a combination
13 of supercritical fluid chromatography (SFC) with simulated moving bed (SMB)
14 technique for enantioseparation of mitotane. In the second paper², the authors
15 separated the enantiomers of mitotane using Kromasil ® CHI-TBB column and
16 four different carrier gases (mobile phase), i.e., pure CO₂, CO₂ + methanol, CO₂
17 + ethanol, and CO₂ + isopropanol. The range for the concentration of alcohol in
18 the mobile phase was from 2.6 to 4.8 %. The chromatographic separation was
19 performed at 35 °C and 16.0 MPa and the best results were obtained at 4.8 %
20 methanol concentration².

21 In this way, the phase behavior of mitotane in supercritical CO₂ plus a co-
22 solvent is an important information needed to develop separation process that
23 employ the SFC technique. In this sense, we recently published experimental
24 solubility data of mitotane in compressed and/or supercritical CO₂.³ The phase
25 equilibrium data were determined within a temperature range from (298.2 to
26 333.1) K and at pressures up to 22.0 MPa. The Peng-Robinson equation of

1 state (PR-EoS) with classical combining and mixing rules, coupled to an
2 equation for the solid mitotane fugacity, which uses the mitotane sublimation
3 pressure as a reference state, were used to correlate the experimental data.
4 Calculation results, obtained mainly within the ranges of conditions of the
5 experimental data, showed a good agreement between experimental and
6 calculated values.

7 Due to the size and polarity asymmetry of the mitotane + CO₂ system,
8 this binary mixture presents a quite complex phase behavior. The correct
9 modeling of this system, in wide ranges of conditions, is therefore a scientific
10 challenge.

11 Recently, Rodriguez-Reartes et al.⁴ performed phase equilibrium
12 calculations for highly asymmetric systems, such as the propane+n-eicosane
13 and CO₂ + n-eicosane binary mixtures, using path-following methods for
14 tracking entire solid–fluid (SF) and solid–fluid–fluid (SFF) equilibrium curves. In
15 this way, the authors obtained complete SF lines and three-phase equilibrium
16 lines in single runs. More details on the calculation of SFF lines have been
17 recently provided by Rodriguez-Reartes et al.¹⁴ The Peng–Robinson equation of
18 state was used for describing the fluid phases, together with an expression for
19 the fugacity of the pure n-eicosane solid phase, with parameter values that
20 reproduced the pure n-eicosane melting curve¹⁴. The simple model proposed by
21 the authors was able to represent, at least qualitatively, both asymmetric
22 mixtures. Such model¹⁴ has derivatives with respect to temperature that are not
23 discontinuous at the triple point temperature of the heavy component. This is
24 not the case for models such as the one used by Favareto et al.³

1 A recent repetition of part of the experiments of Favareto et al.³ led us
2 to conclude that the phase transition type (either FF or SF) was missidentified in
3 some cases in such previous work. Therefore, the objective here is to provide
4 new and/or revised phase equilibrium data for the system mitotane + CO₂, and
5 new phase equilibrium data for the system mitotane + CO₂ + ethanol. The
6 temperature range of the experiments is from (298 to 333) K and the pressure
7 range is from 3.44 to 21.84 MPa. For gathering the experimental data, we use
8 the synthetic-static method. The core of the equipment is a high-pressure
9 variable-volume view cell. The experimental data of solid-fluid (SF) and fluid-
10 fluid (FF) transitions obtained here for the mitotane + CO₂ system were
11 modeled using the methodology proposed by Rodriguez-Reartes et al.⁴

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2. Experimental

2.1 Materials

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16 The carbon dioxide used here was purchased to White Martins and had a
17 minimum mass fraction purity higher than 0.999. Ethanol standard for gas
18 chromatography was obtained from Sigma Aldrich. Racemic mitotane ((RS)-1-
19 chloro-2-[2,2-dichloro-1-(4-chlorophenyl)-ethyl]-benzene) was acquired from
20 Yick-Vic Chemicals and Pharmaceuticals company (Hong Kong). All materials
21 were used without further purification.

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2.2 Apparatus and procedure

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25 Measurements of the SF, FF and VL (vapor-liquid) transitions were
26 performed using the synthetic-static method in a high-pressure variable-volume

1 view cell used in previous works of our group.^{3,5-9} The equilibrium cell has a
2 maximum internal volume of $25 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3$ and contains a movable piston. It also
3 has two sapphire windows, one for visual observations, 0.025 m i.d. and
4 another lateral one for light entrance, 0.015 m i.d.. The maximum operating
5 temperature and pressure are, respectively, 423 K and 35.0 MPa, The internal
6 cell diameter is 0.018 m.

7 The experimental apparatus has also an absolute pressure transducer
8 (Smar LD 301), with a precision of 0.01 MPa, a portable programmer (Smar, HT
9 201) for the pressure data acquisition, and a syringe pump (ISCO 260D). The
10 pressure transducer used for pressure measurements was calibrated against a
11 digital multimeter HP-34401A model. In the experimental apparatus, the
12 pressure transducer is connected to the movable piston that permits the
13 pressure control inside the cell. The cell is equipped with a water bath and a
14 PID controller (DIGI MEC mark, SHM 112 model). The controller was connected
15 to a thermocouple (J type, with an accuracy of 1.0 K), which was in direct
16 contact with the fluid mixture inside the equilibrium cell. The thermocouple was
17 calibrated using a primary thermometer (Inco term, 47342 model) at four fixed
18 temperatures ranging from (273 to 373) K, providing a temperature control
19 within 1.0 K. Figure 1 shows the experimental apparatus used here to obtain
20 high-pressure phase transition data.

21 Initially, the cell and all lines were flushed out with low-pressure CO₂ to
22 remove residual air. Depending on the desired global composition, an amount
23 of mitotane or mitotane + solvent was weighed on a high precision scale
24 (Ohaus Analytical Standard, with precision of 0.0001 g) and loaded into the cell.
25 Afterwards, the gas was pumped into the cell in order to reach the pre-

1 established global composition. The amount of gas charged was monitored by
2 the change in the total mass of the transfer vessel of the pump. Based on the
3 uncertainties of the mass introduced, it was possible to estimate, through
4 propagation of error analysis,⁴ that the maximum uncertainties in mole fraction
5 values were never greater than 0.11 % for carbon dioxide. Then, the cell
6 content was kept at continuous agitation with a magnetic stirrer and a Teflon-
7 coated stirring bar. After reaching the desired temperature, the cell pressure
8 was increased by applying pressure on the back of the piston with the syringe
9 pump, using CO₂ as an auxiliary fluid, until the system reached a single phase
10 state. At this point, the system was allowed to stabilize for at least 30 minutes.
11 In order to promote a phase transition, the cell pressure was decreased slowly
12 until the incipient formation of another phase was observed. The pressure was
13 then recorded. The previous procedure was repeated at least three times
14 leading to experimental standard deviations in the order of 0.03 MPa. We
15 decided to approach the phase transition condition through a set of single-
16 phase states rather than through a set of two-phase states since the mixing of
17 the contents of the equilibrium cell may be less efficient for two-phase systems
18 than for single-phase systems. On the other hand, the search for the pressure
19 of appearance of a new phase is a well established procedure¹⁶⁻²⁰.

20

21 **3. Modeling of the phase behavior of the CO₂ + Mitotane system**

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23 In this work we modeled the phase behavior of the binary system carbon
24 dioxide + mitotane. We present calculated phase envelopes which are
25 constituted by segments corresponding to fluid-fluid (FF) and solid-fluid (SF)

1 equilibrium transitions. We used the experimental data obtained here to fit the
2 needed parameters.

3 We use the Peng-Robinson Equation of State (PR-EOS)¹⁰ for calculating
4 component fugacities in fluid state for pure compounds and mixtures. We
5 obtained the binary interaction parameters (corresponding to classical
6 combining and mixing rules, i.e., k_{ij} and l_{ij}) for the PR-EOS by adjusting all the
7 fluid-fluid (FF) equilibrium data reported in Table 1. The resulting k_{ij} and l_{ij}
8 values are given in Table 2. For mitotane, we used the pure compound critical
9 properties and acentric factor reported by Favareto et al.³. For CO₂ we took
10 such information from the DIPPR database²¹. For solid-fluid equilibrium
11 calculations, we assumed that the solid phase is pure mitotane. The fugacity of
12 the pure heavy component (mitotane) in solid state at system temperature (T)
13 and pressure (P), is given in this work by equation 1 of Appendix A. The values,
14 used in this work, for the pure mitotane constants required for evaluating the
15 variable U of such equation are reported in Table 3, and their meaning is
16 explained in Appendix A and in Table 3. We obtained the pure mitotane
17 parameters $C1$, $C2$, $C3$ and Δv^{S-L} by fitting all the solid-fluid (SF) equilibrium
18 experimental data reported in Table 1.

19 The set of equations for phase equilibrium calculations arises from
20 imposing the classical necessary conditions: equal temperature, pressure, and
21 component fugacities in all phases. With regard to the calculation algorithms,
22 we used numerical continuation methods for all phase equilibrium
23 computations.

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25 **4. Results and Discussion**

1

2 4.1 Experimental Results

3

4 Table 1 presents the experimental data of phase transitions for the
5 CO₂(1) + mitotane(2) systems obtained at the global CO₂ mole fractions $x_1 =$
6 0.9993, 0.9990, 0.9986, 0.9979, 0.9976, and 0.9972. The difference between
7 the data that Table 1 reports and the data by Favareto et al.³ lies, on one hand,
8 on the corrected identification of the phase transition type for ten data points,
9 and, on the other hand, in the appearance, in Table 1, of eight new data points
10 obtained in the present work (four of them correspond to $x_1 = 0.9990$). The
11 correct identification of the phase transitions could be achieved because the
12 experimental apparatus used in the present work permits a better visualization
13 of the phase transitions than the one used by Favareto et al.³

14 In each isopleth, we observe solid-fluid (SF) and fluid-fluid (FF)
15 transitions. The data shown in Table 1 are plotted in the Figure 2 for better
16 visualization and understanding of phase behavior of the system. From this
17 figure we observe that all isopleths present SF transition segments at lower
18 pressures and FF transitions at higher pressures. For all points in Table 1, the
19 system is a homogeneous fluid at a pressure greater than the reported
20 pressure, and it is a heterogeneous system otherwise.

21 In order to obtain the phase transition data for ternary mixtures of CO₂ (1)
22 + ethanol (2) + mitotane(3), two solutions with different concentrations of
23 mitotane in ethanol were prepared: 0.04 moles and 0.40 moles of mitotane per
24 kg of ethanol. The solution concentration uncertainty was lower than 0.01
25 moles.kg⁻¹. Tables 4 and 5 present results of ternary CO₂ (1) + ethanol (2) +

1 mitotane (3) mixtures at two mitotane concentrations. In Table 4, the
2 experimental data refer to vapor-liquid transitions at mitotane concentration of
3 $0.04 \text{ moles.kg}^{-1}$, where we identify vapor-liquid bubble point (BP) and dew point
4 (DP) transitions. Table 5 presents the vapor-liquid transitions for mitotane
5 concentration of $0.40 \text{ moles.kg}^{-1}$. Again, bubble point (BP) and dew point (DP)
6 transitions were identified. For all points in Tables 4 and 5, the system is a
7 homogenous fluid at a pressure greater than the reported pressure, and it is a
8 heterogeneous fluid-fluid system otherwise.

9 Figure 3 provides a comparison (p-x diagram) between experimental VLE
10 (vapor-liquid equilibrium) data obtained here for the ternary $\text{CO}_2(1) + \text{ethanol}(2)$
11 $+ \text{mitotane}(3)$ mixture at concentration of mitotane $0.04 \text{ moles.kg}^{-1}$ with binary
12 data of $\text{CO}_2(1) + \text{ethanol}(2)$ (without mitotane) from the literature at 303 and 333
13 K.¹¹⁻¹² . Figure 4 presents a similar comparison but now the ternary mixture has
14 a mitotane concentration of $0.40 \text{ moles.kg}^{-1}$.

15 Figure 3 shows that the low concentration of mitotane does not lead to
16 significant changes in the transition pressures when the ternary system is
17 compared to the corresponding binary system (without mitotane). However,
18 Figure 4 shows that a higher concentration of mitotane leads to important
19 changes in equilibrium conditions. For the concentration of $0.40 \text{ moles.kg}^{-1}$,
20 there are large differences between the ternary experimental data measured
21 here and the binary data from the literature, mainly in the region of lower
22 concentration of CO_2 .

23 In this work, we made not attempt to model the vapor-liquid equilibrium of
24 the system $\text{CO}_2(1) + \text{ethanol}(2) + \text{mitotane}(3)$.

25

1 4.2 Modeling Results

2

3 In Figure 5f we present a phase envelope, including both solid-fluid (SF)
4 and fluid-fluid (FF) transitions, for the CO₂(1) + mitotane(2) mixture, calculated
5 using the PR-EOS and eq (1), at 0.0028 mitotane mole fraction, i.e., at the
6 highest mitotane concentration shown in Table 1. At high pressure and low
7 temperature, we observe a SF transition segment that goes to low pressure and
8 intersects a liquid-vapor equilibrium line (dew point) at about 16.7 MPa. This
9 point corresponds to a three-phase (solid-liquid-vapor) equilibrium at 0.0028
10 mitotane mole fraction. The liquid-vapor (LV) segment (dew line) that originates
11 at such three-phase point goes through a maximum in pressure and then
12 through a maximum in temperature. At very low pressure, the LV transition line
13 intersects another SF transition segment that is hard to see in Figure 5f due to
14 the linear scale in pressure. This SF segment is better visualized in Figure 6f,
15 where a logarithmic scale for pressure is used. In this figure we observe clearly
16 the second three phase solid-liquid-vapor point at about 0.01 MPa. Notice that
17 the abbreviation FF located inside the heterogeneous region of, e.g., Fig. 5f,
18 indicates a point where the phase condition is a fluid-fluid equilibrium. Similarly,
19 the abbreviation SF is written at a point where the phase condition is a solid-
20 fluid equilibrium.

21 Notice that the PR-EoS and eq (1) capture the qualitative behavior
22 observed experimentally in the laboratory. For example, at the temperature and
23 pressure conditions of point A in Figure 5f, the model gives a homogeneous
24 fluid state. If we decrease the pressure at constant temperature, i.e., at 313 K,
25 from point A to point C, we reach a heterogeneous solid-fluid condition at point

1 C. At such temperature, the limit between the homogeneous and
2 heterogeneous states is located at point B, where the fluid phase is saturated in
3 mitotane (at equilibrium with a pure mitotane solid phase).

4 From Figure 6f, we notice that the model [PR-EoS and eq (1)] predicts a
5 minimum in temperature for the high-pressure solid-fluid line at 0.0028 mitotane
6 mole fraction. Thus, for this isopleth composition, at any temperature lower than
7 about 304 K (which is approximately the temperature of the minimum), it would
8 not be possible to observe a (dense) homogeneous phase even at very high
9 pressure conditions (at least up to 200 MPa which is the maximum pressure of
10 the actual calculations carried out for generating Figures 5f and 6f).

11 In Figure 5f and according to the model, at about 20.0 MPa and 500 K,
12 the system is a homogenous fluid (made of only one phase). Then, by
13 decreasing the temperature while keeping the pressure constant at 20.0 MPa, a
14 second fluid phase appears when the dew line is crossed for the first time. The
15 system presents two phases (FF system). The two coexisting fluid phases
16 remain within a large temperature range, until the FF line (dew line) is
17 intersected again. A further decrease in temperature takes the system back to a
18 homogeneous fluid phase condition. By decreasing the temperature even more,
19 the solid-fluid line is intersected and a solid phase, pure mitotane, appears. This
20 solid-fluid coexistence remains even at very low temperatures.

21 The negative slope of the high-pressure solid-fluid line in Figure 5f,
22 predicted by the model [PR-EoS and eq (1)], corresponds to a retrograde
23 solidification with respect to pressure, which is characterized by the
24 disappearance of a solid phase with the increase in pressure, as it happens
25 when going from point C to point A (through the intersection point B) in Figure

1 5f. However, according to the model, if the pressure is further increased from
2 point A, at constant temperature, a new intersection point is reached (see
3 Figure 6f), and a solid phase, pure mitotane, re-appears. Thus, for the model
4 [which predicts a change in slope for the high pressure solid-fluid line (Figure
5 6f)], the normal behavior is recovered at high enough pressure.

6 Figure 5a shows a phase envelope obtained from the [PR-EoS and eq
7 (1)] model (lines) and also shows experimental data (points) for the CO₂(1) +
8 mitotane(2) mixture at 0.0007 mitotane mole fraction (the lowest mitotane
9 concentration in Table 1). This figure presents, for the model, a high-pressure
10 SF equilibrium segment (S_I) that exists in a narrow temperature range. A bubble
11 point segment connects the SF segment S_I with a second SF segment S_{II} ,
12 which has a positive slope and has a wider temperature range than S_I . The S_{II}
13 SF segment intersects a dew point line at higher temperature. The calculated
14 dew and S_{II} segments are consistent with the experimental data obtained in our
15 laboratory (circles shown in Figures 5a and 6a). Indeed, we looked for such
16 consistency while fitting the parameters of the model. Similar to the previous
17 system shown in Figures 5f and 6f, another SF equilibrium segment (S_{III})
18 appears at very low pressures. Comparing the calculated dew and S_{II} segments
19 with the FF and SF experimental data shown in Figure 5a, we conclude that,
20 clearly, the model [PR-EoS and eq (1)] correlates very well the SF data and
21 provides a fair description of the FF data. However, the model over predicts
22 both, the temperature and the pressure of the intersection point of the (SF) S_{II}
23 and dew (FF) segments, i.e., of the three-phase point.

24 In Figure 5a, the calculation results obtained with the model suggest that
25 there is a pressure range within which it is possible to reach, at constant

1 pressure, solid-fluid transitions from an initial homogeneous fluid state, either by
2 increasing the temperature (retrograde behavior) or by decreasing the
3 temperature (normal behavior). Of both phenomena, the retrograde behavior is
4 confirmed by our experimental data (filled circles) in Figure 5a. Consider for
5 example a constant pressure of 8.0 MPa. From an initial SF condition, i.e., a
6 point at 8.0 MPa located just to the right of the S_{II} segment, a decrease in
7 temperature takes the system to a single phase region after the SF S_{II} segment
8 is crossed (retrograde melting at constant pressure, RMCP). A further decrease
9 in temperature takes the system again to a SF condition at low enough
10 temperature (normal solidification at constant pressure) after the SF S_I segment
11 is intersected. This complex behavior is due to the SF line S_{II} that exists at
12 intermediate temperatures. It should be clear that for a system showing RMCP
13 it is possible to melt a solid phase by decreasing the temperature. The
14 phenomenon of retrograde melting at constant pressure could be attributed to
15 the non-linear decrease of the solvent density (CO_2), and the corresponding
16 behavior of its dielectric constant (reduction of solvent power), when
17 temperature is raised under conditions close to the critical conditions of the
18 solvent (carbon dioxide). Figure 6a shows the phase diagram of Figure 5a but in
19 logarithmic scale for the pressure, for better visualization of the phase behavior
20 in a larger pressure range. We notice that the SF transition line S_I presents a
21 minimum in temperature indicative of mitotane retrograde crystallization at
22 constant temperature (RCCT). We have not performed experiments under the
23 conditions of the S_I SF segment. Thus, the RCCT at low temperature is a
24 prediction by the model [PR-EoS and eq (1)] that would have to be confirmed
25 through additional experiments. The solid-fluid segments S_I and S_{III} predicted

1 by the model conform to the common sense expectation that at low enough
2 temperature a solid phase must be present in the system. This must happen
3 even in the case of existence of RMCP at an intermediate temperature range
4 (segment S_{II}).

5 Notice that the segment S_{II} (Figure 5a) presents not only RMCP but also
6 RCCT, since an increase in pressure at constant temperature takes the system
7 from the solid-fluid state to the homogeneous fluid state if the segment S_{II} is
8 crossed. It is clear that for segment S_{II} the experimental data support the
9 conclusion that the system CO_2 + mitotane presents, at intermediate
10 temperatures, retrograde melting (or retrograde crystallization) both, at constant
11 temperature and at constant pressure.

12 Figures 5b and 6b show the phase envelope obtained from the model
13 [PR-EoS and eq (1), lines] and also show experimental data (points) for the
14 $CO_2(1)$ + mitotane(2) mixture at 0.001 mitotane mole fraction. For this isopleth,
15 a bubble point line at intermediate temperatures (such as the one shown in
16 Figures 5a and 6a for a lower mitotane concentration) does not exist. However,
17 the retrograde melting at constant pressure (RMCP) behavior remains. A
18 similar phase diagram is observed for 0.0014 mitotane mole fraction (shown in
19 Figures 5c and 6c).

20 Figures 5d and 6d, and 5e and 6e show phase diagrams obtained from
21 the model (lines) and also show experimental data (points) for the $CO_2(1)$ +
22 mitotane(2) mixture at 0.0021 and 0.0024 mitotane mole fraction, respectively.
23 These phase diagrams are similar to that of 0.0028 mitotane mole fraction
24 shown in Figures 5f and 6f. According to the model, for these isopleth
25 conditions the mixtures present no bubble point line at intermediate

1 temperatures, neither retrograde melting at constant pressure.

2 Even though the PR-EoS with classical combining and mixing rules
3 coupled to eq (1) of Appendix A describes reasonably well the phase diagrams
4 presented here, it might be possible to improve the model performance by using
5 a non-classical mixing rule. The need for more complex mixing rules (MRs),
6 such as the Wong-Sandler²⁴ MR, or the cubic mixing rules^{13,22}, is typically
7 expected for highly asymmetric binary systems as mitotane-CO₂ studied here.

8 It is clear that we have adjusted six parameters for the system
9 CO₂+mitotane, i.e., parameters k_{ij} , l_{ij} , C1, C2, C3 and Δv^{S-L} . However, all
10 these parameters were not fitted simultaneously. Parameters k_{ij} , l_{ij} were fitted
11 first, using only fluid-fluid equilibrium information. Parameters C1, C2, C3 and
12 Δv^{S-L} were fit next, using only solid-fluid equilibrium data. During this second
13 step, parameters k_{ij} and l_{ij} remained fixed and set at the values of Table 2.
14 Notice that although in this work we obtained parameters k_{ij} , l_{ij} , C1, C2, C3
15 and Δv^{S-L} from binary information, strictly, only parameters k_{ij} , l_{ij} are binary,
16 while parameters C1, C2, C3 and Δv^{S-L} are pure compound parameters.

17 If pure mitotane solid-liquid equilibrium data, in a wide enough pressure
18 range, had been available, it would have been possible to obtain the constants
19 C1, C2, C3 from such pure mitotane experimental data, as done for n-Eicosane
20 by Rodriguez-Reartes et al.^{4,14}. Next, parameter Δv^{S-L} , i.e., the only remaining
21 degree of freedom, would have been fitted from mixture solid-fluid equilibrium
22 data^{4,14}. The (indeed different) approach we chose in this work to fit the model
23 parameters was defined on the basis of the available experimental data. The
24 values for the constants C1, C2, C3 reported in Table 3 are such that the

1 calculated pure mitotane liquid-solid equilibrium curve (not shown in this article)
2 has a positive slope at least up to 200 MPa.

3 Notice that the computation of constants C1, C2, C3 from pure
4 compound solid-liquid equilibrium data is analogous to imposing the
5 reproduction of the pure compound vapor-liquid equilibrium curve for models of
6 the equation of state type, designed for describing equilibria between fluid
7 phases.

8 The alternative approach of using mixing rules, within the PR-EOS, more
9 flexible with regard to composition and temperature²², i.e., the use of a number
10 of binary interaction parameters greater than two, when reproducing fluid-fluid
11 equilibrium data with the model; might have reduced the need for non-zero
12 parameters (C1, C2, C3 and Δv^{S-L}) in eq (1) of Appendix A, when reproducing
13 the solid-fluid equilibrium data.

14 Models which, because of their theoretical basis, are often regarded as
15 more advanced than the one used here, e.g., the PC-SAFT²³ EOS for
16 describing fluids phases; may lead to inconsistent behavior due to the
17 appearance of liquid-liquid coexistence curves for pure fluids, i.e., of a
18 phenomenon that has never been experimentally observed²³.

19

20 **5. Conclusion**

21

22 Phase transition measurements for binary mixtures of CO₂ (1) + mitotane
23 (2) and ternary mixtures of CO₂ (1) + ethanol (2) + mitotane (3) are provided
24 here.

25 For binary mixtures of CO₂ (1) + mitotane (2) we provide experimental

1 data on solid-fluid (SF) and fluid-fluid (FF) transitions for six isopleths (mitotane
2 mole fractions of 0.0007, 0.001, 0.0014, 0.0021, 0.0024, and 0.0028).

3 The experimental data for CO₂(1) + mitotane(2) at 0.0007, 0.001, and
4 0.0014 mitotane mole fraction show retrograde melting (or retrograde
5 crystallization) at constant pressure, and also at constant temperature, i.e., they
6 show that the solid phase is melted either by decreasing the temperature at
7 constant pressure or by increasing the pressure at constant temperature.

8

9 This behavior is properly captured by a model built by combining the
10 Peng-Robinson equation of state (PR-EoS, with classical combining and mixing
11 rules) with an equation that describes the fugacity of pure compounds in solid
12 state, i.e., equation (1) of Appendix A . The model also predicts, for all
13 isopleths studied here, the occurrence, at low temperatures, of retrograde
14 mitotane melting at constant temperature, which corresponds to the existence,
15 in the low temperature range, of a point of minimum temperature in the
16 predicted SF equilibrium line. The existence of this phenomenon, at low
17 temperatures, for the CO₂(1) + mitotane(2) system should be regarded, for the
18 time being, as a presumption. Additional experiments should be performed to
19 confirm or reject this expectation. Gregorowicz¹⁵ has analyzed the criteria for
20 the existence of retrograde melting at constant temperature.

21 The numerical continuation methods used in the calculations were
22 essential to track the highly non-linear solid-fluid equilibrium curves computed
23 with the model.

24 The calculated isopleths have a temperature range wider than the
25 temperature range studied experimentally. In spite of the potentially important

1 errors that, from the quantitative point of view, such extrapolations may carry,
2 the calculation results obtained in the present work, over wide ranges of
3 conditions, are useful to enhance our understanding of the possible qualitative,
4 highly non-ideal, behavior of the present and related systems.

5 Here we also provide liquid-vapor equilibrium data of ternary mixtures of
6 CO₂ (1) + ethanol (2) + mitotane (3) for two concentrations of mitotane in
7 ethanol: 0.04 moles and 0.40 moles of mitotane per kg of ethanol. A low
8 concentration of mitotane does not lead to significant changes in the transition
9 pressures with respect to the mitotane-free binary system. In contrast, a higher
10 concentration of mitotane produces important changes in the equilibrium
11 conditions.

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1 Literature Cited

- 2
- 3 (1) Dias, R. M.; Santana, C. C. Transferência de Massa e Efeitos
4 Termodinâmicos na Separação do Fármaco Mitotano por Cromatografia
5 Líquida de Alta Eficiência (in portuguese). *Proceedings of IV Congresso*
6 *Brasileiro de Termodinâmica Aplicada*, Recife, Brazil (2008).
7
- 8 (2) Antelo, F.; Santana, C. C.; Barreto Jr, A. G.; Alves, T. L. M.
9 Enantioseparation of Mitotane by Supercritical Fluid Chromatography on
10 Kromasil Chi-Tbb at 160 Bar. *Proceedings of II Iberoamerican Conference*
11 *on Supercritical Fluids – PROSCIBA*. 2010, Natal-RN, Brazil.
12
- 13 (3) Favareto, R.; Pereira, J. R. D.; Santana, C. C.; Madureira, E. H.; Cabral, V.
14 F.; Tavares, F. W.; Cardozo-Filho, L., High-pressure phase diagram of the
15 drug mitotane in compressed and/or supercritical CO₂. *The Journal of*
16 *Chemical Thermodynamics*. 2010, 42, (2), 286-290.
17
- 18 (4) Rodriguez-Reartes, S. B.; Cismondi, M.; Franceschi, E.; Corazza, M. L.;
19 Oliveira, J. V.; Zabaloy, M. S., High-pressure phase equilibria of systems
20 carbon dioxide + n-eicosane and propane + n-eicosane. *The Journal of*
21 *Supercritical Fluids*. 2009, 50, (3), 193-202.
22
- 23 (5) Carvalho, J. R. N; Corazza, M. L.; Cardozo-Filho, L. ; Meireles, M. A. A.
24 Phase Equilibrium for (Camphor + CO₂), (Camphor + Propane) and
25 (Camphor + CO₂ + Propane). *Journal of Chemical and Engineering Data*,
26 2006, 51, (3), 997-1000.
27
- 28 (6) Favareto, R; Cabral, V. F.; Corazza, M. L.; Cardozo-Filho, L. Vapor-liquid
29 and solid-fluid equilibrium for progesterone + CO₂, progesterone +
30 propane, and progesterone + n-butane systems at elevated pressures. *J.*
31 *Supercrit. Fluids*. 2008, 45, (2), 161-170.
32
- 33 (7) Souza, A. T. ; Benazzi, T. L. ; Grings, M. B.; Cabral, V. F. ; Silva, E. A. ;
34 Cardozo Filho, L.; Antunes, O. A. C. Supercritical extraction process and
35 phase equilibrium of Candeia (*Eremanthus erythropappus*) oil using
36 supercritical carbon dioxide. *The Journal of Supercritical Fluids*. 2008, 47,
37 182-187.
38
- 39 (8) Favareto, R.; Fregadolli, P.H.; Cabral, V.F.; Antunes, O.A.C.; Cardozo-
40 Filho, L. Phase Equilibria of Acrylonitrile and p-Bromobenzaldehyde in
41 Carbon Dioxide. *J. Chem. Eng. Data*, 2008, 53 (5), pp 1080–1084. DOI:
42 10.1021/je700448v
43
- 44 (9) Moura, L. S.; Favareto, R.; Leal, P. F. ; Corazza, M.L.; Cardozo-Filho, L;
45 Meireles, M. A. A. Phase-Equilibrium Measurements for CO₂ + Priprioca
46 Extract at High Pressures. *The Journal of Supercritical Fluids*. 2009, 48,
47 126-130.
48

- 1 (10) Peng, D.-Y.; Robinson, D. B., A New Two-Constant Equation of State.
2 *Industrial & Engineering Chemistry Fundamentals*. **1976**, 15, (1), 59-64.
3
- 4 (11) Joung, S. N.; Yoo, C. W.; Shin, H. Y.; Kim, S. Y.; Yoo, K-P; Lee, C. S.; and
5 Huh, W. S.; "Measurements and correlation of high-pressure VLE of binary
6 CO₂-alcohol systems (methanol, ethanol, 2-methoxyethanol and 2-
7 ethoxyethanol)", *Fluid Phase Equilibria*, **2001**, 185, 219-230.
8
- 9 (12) Chiu, H.-Y.; Lee, M.-J.; and Lin, H.-M.; "Vapor-Liquid phase boundaries of
10 binary mixtures of carbon dioxide with ethanol and acetone", *J. Chem.*
11 *Eng. Data*. **2008**, 53, 2393–2402.
12
- 13 (13) Zabaloy, M.S. Cubic Mixing Rules. *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* **2008**, 47, 5063–
14 5079
15
- 16 (14) Rodriguez-Reartes, S.B.; Cismondi, M.; and Zabaloy, M.S. Computation of
17 solid–fluid–fluid equilibria for binary asymmetric mixtures in wide ranges of
18 conditions. *The Journal of Supercritical Fluids*. **2011**, 57, 9–24
19
- 20 (15) Gregorowicz, J. Phase behaviour in the vicinity of the three-phase solid–
21 liquid–vapour line in asymmetric nonpolar systems at high pressures. *Fluid*
22 *Phase Equilib.*, 2006, 240, 29-39
23
- 24 (16) Deiters, U.K.; Schneider, G.M. High Pressure Phase Equilibria:
25 Experimental Methods. *Fluid Phase Equilibria*. **1986**, 29, 145-160.
26
- 27 (17) Suppes, Q.J.; Mchugh, M.A. Phase Behavior of the Carbon Dioxide-
28 Styrene System. *J Chem. Eng. Data* **1989**, 34, 310-312.
29
- 30 (18) Christov, M.; Dohrn, R. High-Pressure Fluid Phase Equilibria: Experimental
31 Methods and Systems Investigated (1988–1993). *Fluid Phase Equilibria*.
32 **1995**, 106, 213–282.
33
- 34 (19) Christov, M.; Dohrn, R. High-Pressure Fluid Phase Equilibria: Experimental
35 Methods and Systems Investigated (1994–1999). *Fluid Phase Equilibria*.
36 **2002**, 202, 153-218.
37
- 38 (20) Ashour, I.; Hammam, H. Equilibrium Solubility of Pure Mono-, Di-, and
39 Trilaurin in Supercritical Carbon Dioxide Experimental Measurements and
40 Model Prediction, *J. Supercritical Fluids*. **1993**, 6, 3-8.
41
- 42 (21) DIPPR 801, Evaluated Process Design Data, Public Release in, American
43 Institute of Chemical Engineers, Design Institute for Physical Property
44 Data, BYU-DIPPR, Thermophysical Properties Laboratory, Provo, Utah,
45 2003.
46
- 47 (22) Cismondi, M., Mollerup, J.M., Zabaloy, M.S. Equation of state modeling of
48 the phase equilibria of asymmetric CO₂ + n-alkane binary systems using
49 mixing rules cubic with respect to mole fraction. *Journal of Supercritical*
50 *Fluids*, **2010**, 55, 671-681

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(23) Privat, R. ; Gani, R. and Jaubert, J.N. Are safe results obtained when the PC-SAFT equation of state is applied to ordinary pure chemicals? Fluid Phase Equilibria, **2010**, 295, 76–92.

(24) Wong, D. S. H. and Sandler, S. I. A theoretically correct mixing rule for cubic equations of state. AIChE Journal, **1992**, 38, 671–680. doi: 10.1002/aic.690380505

1 APPENDIX A: Thermodynamic model

2

3 The model used in this work for describing phase equilibria involving fluid and
4 solid phases is the same than the model used in previous works^{4,14}. To describe
5 the fluid state of a binary mixture of a light component (labeled “1”) and a heavy
6 component (labeled “2”), we use a pressure-explicit equation of state (EOS),
7 i.e., a relationship between the absolute pressure (P), the absolute temperature
8 (T), the mixture molar volume (ν) and the mixture composition z_2 , where z_2 is
9 the mole fraction of component “2”. We represent such relationship as
10 $P = h_{pVT}(T, z_2, \nu)$, where the form of function h_{pVT} corresponds to the adopted
11 EOS, e.g., to the Peng-Robinson (PR)¹⁰ EOS, i.e., the EOS that we used in this
12 work. The h_{pVT} function, imposes the expression for the fugacity of component
13 “ i ” in the fluid mixture (\hat{f}_i). Thus, \hat{f}_i depends on the same variables than
14 function h_{pVT} , i.e., $\hat{f}_i = \hat{f}_i(T, z_2, \nu)$. Indeed, this last functional relationship also
15 corresponds in this work to the PR-EOS¹⁰.

16

17 Due to the high asymmetry of the binary system that we consider in this work,
18 we assume that a given solid phase is made of only the pure heavy component
19 (component “2”, i.e., mitotane in this work). Thus, for performing equilibrium
20 calculations, we need an equation relating the fugacity of the pure component
21 “2” in solid state to the absolute pressure (P) and to the absolute temperature
22 (T) of the system. We define, mathematically, the fugacity of the pure heavy
23 component “2” in solid state at T and P , i.e., $f_2^S(T, P, \nu_o)$, (where ν_o actually
24 depends on T and P) as follows:

25

$$f_2^S(T, P, \nu_o) = \hat{f}_2(T, 1, \nu_o) \exp(U) \quad (1)$$

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2 In Eq. (1), ν_o is the molar volume of the pure heavy component (component
3 “2”), in (subcooled hypothetical) liquid state, at T and P . Such pure liquid has a
4 fugacity $\hat{f}_2(T, 1, \nu_o)$ [first factor within the right hand side of Eq. (1)]. Notice that

5 expression $\hat{f}_2(T, 1, \nu_o)$ simply states that the function $\hat{f}_i = \hat{f}_i(T, z_2, \nu)$, with

6 subscript “ i ” set equal to “2”, is evaluated at $z_2 = 1$ and at $\nu = \nu_o$, i.e., that the

7 computed fugacity corresponds to a liquid made of the pure heavy compound,

8 having such pure liquid a molar volume equal to ν_o . Both, ν_o and $\hat{f}_2(T, 1, \nu_o)$

9 are given in this work by the PR-EOS¹⁰. The exponential factor in Eq. (1) relates

10 [through eq (1)] the hypothetical liquid state with the solid state for a pure

11 substance at given temperature and pressure. The variable U , which depends

12 on T and P , is defined as follows:

13

$$U = \frac{\Delta \nu^{S-L}}{RT_p} \left[C_1 \left(1 - \frac{T_p}{T} \right) + C_2 \left(\frac{T_p}{T} - 1 + \ln \left(\frac{T}{T_p} \right) \right) + C_3 \left(\frac{T}{2T_p} - 1 + \frac{T_p}{2T} \right) + \frac{T_p}{T} (P - P_p) \right] \quad (2)$$

14

15 In Eq. (2), the constants T_p , P_p , $\Delta \nu^{S-L}$, C_1 , C_2 and C_3 (see Table 3)

16 correspond to the pure heavy component (component “2”). $\Delta \nu^{S-L}$ is the solid-

17 liquid molar volume difference ($\nu_{solid} - \nu_{liquid}$). The constants C_1 , C_2 and C_3

18 characterize the pure heavy component solid-liquid equilibrium curve (P vs. T

19 melting curve). R is the universal gas constant.

20

1 For computing $f_2^S(T, P, \nu_o)$ at set T and P , we would first calculate ν_o from
2 the adopted EOS [$P - h_{pVT}(T, 1, \nu_o) = 0$], next we would compute $\hat{f}_2(T, 1, \nu_o)$,
3 then U from Eq. (2), and, finally, plug the results into the right hand side of Eq.
4 (1), to obtain the value of $f_2^S(T, P, \nu_o)$. We stress that the phase type for
5 $f_2^S(T, P, \nu_o)$ is “solid” while the phase type for $\hat{f}_2(T, 1, \nu_o)$ is “liquid”, and that
6 both fugacities correspond to the same T and P values.

7

8 The variable ν_o , i.e., a property of a pure liquid, appears as an argument for the
9 fugacity of the pure solid [on the left hand side of Eq. (1)] because the fugacity
10 of the pure solid is partially computed from the fugacity of the pure liquid, i.e.,
11 from a liquid-state reference fugacity, being the temperature and pressure for
12 such reference fugacity the same than the temperature and pressure of the
13 solid.

14

15 The calculation of a binary phase equilibrium point requires solving the
16 isofugacity condition for component “1” in all fluid phases and for component “2”
17 in all fluid phases and in the solid phase (if present), after imposing the
18 constraint of uniform pressure and uniform temperature throughout the
19 heterogeneous system.

20

21 More details on the model used here were given by Rodriguez-Reartes et al.¹⁴.

22

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Table 1. Experimental Solid-Fluid (SF) and Fluid-Fluid (FF) transition data for CO₂ (1) + mitotane (2) binary mixtures.

T	P	σ	Transition	T	P	σ	Transition
K	MPa	MPa	type	K	MPa	MPa	Type
$x_1 = 0.9993, x_2 = 0.0007$				$x_1 = 0.9976, x_2 = 0.0024$			
298	6.65	0.01	SF	313	16.33	0.02	SF
303	7.96	0.06	SF	323	18.23	0.02	FF
313	10.21	0.06	SF	333	20.03	0.02	FF
313	10.51	0.05	FF	$x_1 = 0.9972, x_2 = 0.0028$			
323	12.65	0.09	FF	313	18.53	0.02	SF
333	14.58	0.01	FF	323	20.00	0.02	FF
$x_1 = 0.9990, x_2 = 0.001$				333	21.84	0.02	FF
303	8.13	0.04	SF				
313	10.62	0.02	SF				
323	12.55	0.02	FF				
333	14.42	0.01	FF				
$x_1 = 0.9986, x_2 = 0.0014$							
298	9.51	0.10	SF				
303	10.52	0.12	SF				
313	12.19	0.04	SF				
313	12.49	0.02	FF				
323	14.85	0.03	FF				
333	16.84	0.04	FF				
$x_1 = 0.9979, x_2 = 0.0021$							
313	14.57	0.07	SF				
313	15.03	0.04	FF				
323	16.92	0.05	FF				
333	19.41	0.01	FF				

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Table 2 – Binary interaction parameters for the PR-EoS¹⁰		
System	k_{ij}	l_{ij}
Carbon Dioxide (1) + Mitotane (2)	0.161	0.230

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Table 3. Mitotane constants for equation (1) in APPENDIX A.

T_p / K^*	353.15
P_p / MPa^{**}	2.7312E-05
$\Delta v^{s-L} / (m^3/Kmol)$	-0.11640
C_1 / MPa	-1596.941
C_2 / MPa	115214.836
C_3 / MPa	-134857.377

* Taken from reference 3. ** P_p = PR-EOS¹⁰ pure compound vapor-liquid equilibrium pressure at the triple point temperature T_p .

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Table 4. Experimental Vapor-Liquid transition data for CO₂ (1) + ethanol(2) + mitotane (3) ternary mixtures at 0.04 moles.kg⁻¹ mitotane concentration in ethanol (CO₂ - free basis).

T	P	σ	Transition	T	P	σ	Transition
K	MPa	MPa	type	K	MPa	Mpa	Type
$x_1 = 0.2085$				$x_1 = 0.7092$			
303	3.44	0.01	BP	303	5.96	0.01	BP
313	3.98	0.01	BP	313	7.24	0.01	BP
323	4.53	0.02	BP	323	8.50	0.01	BP
333	5.01	0.01	BP	333	9.84	0.01	BP
$x_1 = 0.3203$				$x_1 = 0.8072$			
303	4.61	0.01	BP	303	6.18	0.01	BP
313	5.36	0.01	BP	313	7.49	0.01	BP
323	6.11	0.01	BP	323	8.82	0.05	BP
333	6.91	0.03	BP	333	10.16	0.01	BP
$x_1 = 0.4104$				$x_1 = 0.8653$			
303	5.18	0.01	BP	303	6.16	0.01	BP
313	6.16	0.03	BP	313	7.52	0.01	BP
323	7.06	0.01	BP	323	8.95	0.03	BP
333	8.15	0.03	BP	333	10.28	0.01	BP
$x_1 = 0.5015$				$x_1 = 0.9232$			
303	5.54	0.01	BP	303	6.18	0.01	BP
313	6.62	0.03	BP	313	7.46	0.03	BP
323	7.70	0.02	BP	323	8.85	0.01	BP
333	8.82	0.01	BP	333	10.10	0.03	DP
$x_1 = 0.6011$				$x_1 = 0.9595$			
303	5.98	0.01	BP	303	6.33	0.02	BP
313	7.17	0.01	BP	313	7.66	0.02	BP
323	8.38	0.02	BP	323	8.73	0.03	BP
333	9.73	0.01	BP	333	-	-	-

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Table 5. Experimental Vapor-Liquid transition data for CO₂ (1) + ethanol (2) + mitotane (3) ternary mixtures at 0.40 moles.kg⁻¹ mitotane concentration in ethanol (CO₂ - free basis).

T	P	σ	Transition	T	P	Σ	Transition
K	MPa	MPa	type	K	MPa	Mpa	type
$x_1 = 0.2690$				$x_1 = 0.6602$			
303	5.04	0.01	BP	303	5.96	0.01	BP
313	5.77	0.01	BP	313	7.16	0.02	BP
323	6.57	0.02	BP	323	8.61	0.01	BP
333	7.32	0.02	BP	333	10.06	0.03	BP
$x_1 = 0.3615$				$x_1 = 0.7588$			
303	5.79	0.01	BP	303	5.99	0.01	BP
313	7.03	0.02	BP	313	7.31	0.02	BP
323	8.50	0.02	BP	323	8.82	0.02	BP
333	9.77	0.02	BP	333	10.27	0.01	BP
$x_1 = 0.4611$				$x_1 = 0.8363$			
303	5.75	0.01	BP	303	6.11	0.01	BP
313	7.10	0.01	BP	313	7.53	0.01	BP
323	8.60	0.01	BP	323	8.84	0.01	BP
333	10.05	0.01	BP	333	10.36	0.01	BP
$x_1 = 0.5618$				$x_1 = 0.8656$			
303	5.85	0.01	BP	303	6.33	0.02	BP
313	7.25	0.02	BP	313	7.60	0.01	BP
323	8.72	0.03	BP	323	9.01	0.03	BP
333	10.16	0.01	BP	333	10.41	0.04	DP

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1 **Figure Captions**

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3 **Figure 1** – Experimental Setup. TB – thermostatic bath, SP – syringe pump, EC
4 - equilibrium cell, MS – magnetic stirrer, TC – temperature control, B-EC –
5 equilibrium cell bath, ER – electrical resistance, PT – pressure transducer, PI –
6 pressure indicator, P – movable piston, SSW – side sapphire window, FSW –
7 front sapphire window, V – needle type valve, C – carbon dioxide cylinder, VP -
8 vessel of the pump.

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10 **Figure 2** – Experimental phase equilibrium data for CO₂(1) + mitotane(2)
11 mixtures obtained at global CO₂ concentrations $x_1 = 0.9993$ (–), 0.9990 (M),
12 0.9986 (8), 0.9979 (∇), 0.9976(ψ) and 0.9972(Ξ). For each isopleth, solid-fluid
13 (SF) and fluid-fluid (FF) transitions are indicated by empty and full symbols,
14 respectively.

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16 **Figure 3** - P-x VLE diagram for the CO₂(1)+ ethanol(2) + mitotane(2) mixture at
17 a mitotane concentration in ethanol of 0.04 moles.kg⁻¹. Full symbols are the
18 ternary experimental data from this work: (,) 303 K and (Λ) 333 K. Empty
19 symbols are the experimental data from the literature for the binary system
20 CO₂(1) + ethanol(2): (–) 303 K¹² and (M)333 K¹¹.

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22 **Figure 4** - P-x VLE diagram for the CO₂(1)+ ethanol(2) + mitotane(2) mixture at
23 a mitotane concentration in ethanol of 0.40 moles.kg⁻¹. Full symbols are the
24 ternary experimental data from this work: (,) 303 K and (Λ) 333 K. Empty

1 symbols are the experimental data from the literature for the binary system
2 $\text{CO}_2(1) + \text{ethanol}(2)$: (-) 303 K¹² and (M)333 K¹¹.

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4 **Figure 5** - Phase envelopes for the $\text{CO}_2(1) + \text{mitotane}(2)$ mixture. Mitotane
5 mole fraction values: **Fig. 5a**: 0.0007, **Fig. 5b**: 0.001, **Fig. 5c**: 0.0014, **Fig. 5d**:
6 0.0021, **Fig. 5e**: 0.0024, **Fig. 5f**: 0.0028. ○: experimental fluid-fluid equilibrium
7 data; ●: experimental solid-fluid equilibrium data (experimental data are shown
8 in Table 1). Phase equilibria calculated using the PR-EoS and eq (1) of
9 Appendix A: — solid-fluid, - - - bubble points (fluid-fluid), - - - dew points
10 (fluid-fluid). Note for **Fig. 5f**: At point A, the system is an homogeneous fluid. At
11 points B and C, the system has a heterogeneous solid-fluid state. HR:
12 homogeneous region; FF: fluid-fluid region and SF: solid-fluid region.

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14 **Figure 6** - Phase envelopes, with pressure in log scale, for the $\text{CO}_2(1) +$
15 $\text{mitotane}(2)$ mixture. Mitotane mole fraction values: **Fig. 6a**: 0.0007, **Fig. 6b**:
16 0.001, **Fig. 6c**: 0.0014, **Fig. 6d**: 0.0021, **Fig. 6e**: 0.0024, **Fig. 6f**: 0.0028. ○:
17 experimental fluid-fluid equilibrium data; ●: experimental solid-fluid equilibrium
18 data (experimental data are shown in Table 1). Phase equilibria calculated
19 using the PR-EoS and eq (1) of Appendix A: — solid-fluid, - - - bubble points
20 (fluid-fluid), - - - dew points (fluid-fluid). HR: homogeneous region; FF: fluid-
21 fluid region and SF: solid-fluid region.

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Figure 1 – Experimental Setup. TB – thermostatic bath, SP – syringe pump, EC - equilibrium cell, MS – magnetic stirrer, TC – temperature control, B-EC – equilibrium cell bath, ER – electrical resistance, PT – pressure transducer, PI – pressure indicator, P – movable piston, SSW – side sapphire window, FSW – front sapphire window, V – needle type valve, C – carbon dioxide cylinder, VP - vessel of the pump.

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Figure 2 – Experimental phase equilibrium data for CO₂(1) + mitotane(2) mixtures obtained at global CO₂ concentrations $x_1 = 0.9993$ (–), 0.9990 (M), 0.9986 (8), 0.9979 (∇), 0.9976(ψ) and 0.9972(Ξ). For each isopleth, solid-fluid (SF) and fluid-fluid (FF) transitions are indicated by empty and full symbols, respectively.

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Figure 3 - P-x VLE diagram for the CO₂(1)+ ethanol(2) + mitotane(2) mixture at a mitotane concentration in ethanol of 0.04 moles.kg⁻¹. Full symbols are the ternary experimental data from this work: (●) 303 K and (▲) 333 K. Empty symbols are the experimental data from the literature for the binary system CO₂(1) + ethanol(2): (○) 303 K¹² and (△) 333 K¹¹.

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Figure 4 - P-x VLE diagram for the CO₂(1)+ ethanol(2) + mitotane(2) mixture at a mitotane concentration in ethanol of 0.40 moles.kg⁻¹. Full symbols are the ternary experimental data from this work: (●) 303 K and (▲) 333 K. Empty symbols are the experimental data from the literature for the binary system CO₂(1) + ethanol(2): (○) 303 K¹² and (△) 333 K¹¹.

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Figure 5a

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Figure 5b

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Figure 5c

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Figure 5d

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Figure 5e

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Figure 5f

Figure 5 - Phase envelopes for the CO₂(1) + mitotane(2) mixture. Mitotane mole fraction values: **Fig. 5a:** 0.0007, **Fig. 5b:** 0.001, **Fig. 5c:** 0.0014, **Fig. 5d:** 0.0021, **Fig. 5e:** 0.0024, **Fig. 5f:** 0.0028. ○: experimental fluid-fluid equilibrium data; ●: experimental solid-fluid equilibrium data (experimental data are shown in Table 1). Phase equilibria calculated using the PR-EoS and eq (1) of Appendix A: — solid-fluid, - - - bubble points (fluid-fluid), - · - · - dew points (fluid-fluid). Note for **Fig. 5f:** At point A, the system is an homogeneous fluid. At points B and C, the system has a heterogeneous solid-fluid state. HR: homogeneous region; FF: fluid-fluid region and SF: solid-fluid region.

Figure 6a

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Figure 6c

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Figure 6d

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Figure 6e

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Figure 6f

Figure 6 - Phase envelopes, with pressure in log scale, for the CO₂(1) + mitotane(2) mixture. Mitotane mole fraction values: **Fig. 6a:** 0.0007, **Fig. 6b:** 0.001, **Fig. 6c:** 0.0014, **Fig. 6d:** 0.0021, **Fig. 6e:** 0.0024, **Fig. 6f:** 0.0028. ○: experimental fluid-fluid equilibrium data; ●: experimental solid-fluid equilibrium data (experimental data are shown in Table 1). Phase equilibria calculated using the PR-EoS and eq (1) of Appendix A: — solid-fluid, - - - bubble points (fluid-fluid), - · - · - dew points (fluid-fluid). HR: homogeneous region; FF: fluid-fluid region and SF: solid-fluid region.

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TOC Graphic

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